

EFFICIENCY ENHANCED SCALABLE ORGANIC PHOTOVOLTAICS USING ROLL-TO-ROLL (R2R) NANOIMPRINT LITHOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Light-trapping nanostructures have for decades been researched as a route to enhance the performance of organic solar cells (OSCs). While the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of OSC has reached above 18% recently, industrial compatible devices made by scalable processing in air, using only non-toxic solvents and materials, show significantly lower performance values. Light-trapping nanostructures may improve this, however, the methods for integrating the nanostructures are typically not compatible with industrial scale up. In this work, we demonstrate scalable, industrial compatible, non-fullerene based OSC having integrated light-trapping nanostructures at the back electrodes in the devices. The OSC are made from scalable Roll-to-Roll (R2R) and Sheet-to-Sheet (S2S) processes, and the nanostructures are made using Roll-to-Plate (R2P) nanoimprint lithography. Herewith we show for the first time a fully scalable solution for industrial compatible nanostructured OSC. The nanostructured devices show enhancements in PCE up to 25% compared to reference cells, which arise due to an enhancement in the short-circuit current (15%) via enhanced absorption, and improved charge carrier extraction leading to an enhancement in the fill factor (7%). Optical modelling is utilized to verify the optical effect of the nanostructures. The best devices reach a PCE of 6.5%, which is the highest reported efficiency for air-processed slot-die coated ITO-free flexible PBDB-T:ITIC devices, here using non-toxic solvents.

INTRODUCTION

Organic and hybrid photovoltaics has emerged as promising new photovoltaic technologies due to several appealing features that directly address the current need for significantly increasing the installed photovoltaic capacity in our societies. Organic solar cells (OSCs), which is based on organic semiconductors, is a potential low-cost alternative to existing photovoltaic technologies due to its low material cost, lower manufacturing cost and their potential for large scale manufacturing. The growing demand of photovoltaics challenge integration, and OSCs open up an array of possibilities with their mechanical flexibility¹, light weight^{2,3}, free-form design and colour tuning⁴⁻⁶, semi-transparency^{1,6,7}, low production costs⁸ and a prospect for Roll-to-Roll (R2R) production^{9,10}, making it a promising energy technology for the future energy needs. It also delivers very low energy payback times and low CO₂ emission rates making it an environmentally friendly technology¹¹. The applications for OSCs are vast, for instance in wearable flexible electronics^{12,13}, semi-transparent windows¹⁴, building-integrated solar modules in various colours and shapes in the building facades¹⁵, with much more to come.

In recent years, the state of the art Power Conversion Efficiency (PCE) of single-junction cells reached 18%¹⁶ due to the immense research in synthesis of new donor and especially non-fullerene acceptor materials. The superior performance of non-fullerene OSCs originates from improved optical properties with absorption extending into the infrared region, accessible tunability of energy levels and low energy loss (voltage loss) upon free charge carrier formation, along with, in some cases, enhanced solar cell operating stabilities^{14,17,18}, although this is still a topic under much investigation. The state of art devices in terms of PCE levels are always fabricated using a non-scalable processing technique such as spin coating in an inert atmosphere, which ensures fully controlled interfaces and no material degradation during processing. While this is important when investigating the performance limitations, such fabrication methods have their limitations when adapting to industrial processing conditions due to not only their small active areas, inert

requirements, and low processing throughput, but also due to the use of toxic solvents and rigid substrates, which are all restricted in industrial settings. To adapt to the industrial standards, an up-scalable process with manufacturing in air from high volume production methods should be utilized, to meet the requirements on cost-reduction, and in addition involve only flexible substrates and non-toxic materials and solvents.

Scalable processing of OSCs using R2R technologies, pre-dominantly from slot-die coating, for development of R2R flexible OSCs and modules has been demonstrated in the past^{10,19–28}. Upon up-scaling of OSCs to larger areas using industrial compatible settings, performance drops are always observed. Some of these performance drops arise from the adaptation of flexible substrates, air-processing and for e.g. use of non-toxic solvents²⁹, but also due to too high sheet resistance of electrodes, resulting in a reduction of mainly the short circuit current density (J_{sc}) and the fill factor (FF)^{20,28,30}. To improve some of these parameters, nanostructured light-trapping techniques can be utilized to maximize sunlight absorption, and possibly also the carrier extraction efficiency³¹, leading to overall higher PCE. Several approaches³² have been adopted in the laboratory to increase the sunlight absorption compared to conventional planar devices, such as anti-reflection coatings^{33–36}, Moth eye patterning^{37–39}, light scattering films either on the front or back electrode for light management^{40,41}, periodic nanostructured gratings (NG)^{42–48} and also metal nanoparticles^{49–54}.

Anti-reflection coatings are transparent coatings that are placed on top of solar cells to reduce light reflection, and thereby improving light absorption and PCE. Myers et al. demonstrated the effectiveness of using polymer micro lens array (MLA) deposited on the light incident surface of OSCs by a soft-lithographic moulding method. Such transparent MLA on the surface of the cells reduces the surface reflection and increases the optical path length in the active layer, which results in a relative increase in the overall PCE of 15–60% based on their OSCs architecture³⁶. Moth-eye anti-reflective (AR) structures are arrays of subwavelength protuberances, reducing the amount of

light reflection by creating an effective refractive index gradient. Chen et al. proposed a method of fabricating highly efficient OSCs by patterning biomimetic Moth-eye nanostructure (MEN) into the active layer, and by using an anti-reflective (AR) coating through soft nanoimprint lithography (NIL)³⁹. With the use of Dual side MEN, the OSCs device based on poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl):indene-C60 bis-adduct (P3HT:ICBA) showed a 22% enhancement in light absorption, yielding a PCE of 7.86%. Using a retro-reflective textured sheet on top of glass substrate based OSCs, Eisner et al. improved the light absorption of the device based on PDPPTPT:[60]PCBM active layers⁴¹. The retro-reflective textured sheets were made by a replication technique from cross-linked poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS). With textured sheets, the J_{sc} and PCE increased by 19.7% and 19%, respectively, reaching a PCE of 5.5%.

Introducing periodic NG into solar devices may induce surface plasmons at the interface to the active layer, and simultaneously increase the optical path length of light within the device⁴³. Hara, K. et al. embedded NG structures on the P3HT:PCBM/Au interface in inverted OSCs devices for enhancing the light absorption in the device⁴⁶. The NG structures were fabricated using a nanoimprinting technique with a PDMS stamp. Upon application of NG structures, the devices exhibited increased photocurrent in wavelength regions corresponding to the wavelengths of surface plasmon excitations and waveguide modes, resulting in an improved photocurrent generation with J_{sc} increased by 11%, and PCE increased by 16%, resulting in a PCE of 3.53%. Inclusion of metal nanoparticles in the photoactive medium may enhance the absorption of light by excitation of local surface plasmon resonances (LSPR) and by light scattering^{49,55}. Hamed et al. employed silver sulphide nano-particles (NPs) in inverted OSCs architectures using P3HT:PCBM as a photoactive layer⁴⁹. The devices yielded improvement in the optical and electrical properties of the photoactive layer due to the LSPR and light scattering from silver sulphide NPs, providing an increase in J_{sc} , FF

and PCE, reaching up to 5.15 %. The J_{sc} and PCE were increased by 58% and 121%, respectively, which could be attributed to improved optical absorbance and charge transport processes⁴⁹.

While these examples show a great progress and promise for light-trapping in OSCs, almost all the systems were developed on research scale involving complex fabrication processes for the nanostructures, that cannot easily be up-scaled. Thus, these techniques have not been extensively tested on the large scale, mostly as it is not easily adapted to industrial standards. Soldera, M. et al. demonstrated a R2R hot embossing method to pattern flexible polyethylene using direct laser interference patterning (DLIP)⁵⁶, showing a significant enhancement in performance of spin coated triple-cation perovskite solar cells, due to improved light-trapping provided by the textures. This validate the proof of concept for adopting light management techniques for industrial solar cell applications, however, neither within perovskite nor OSCs, R2R scalable light-trapping integrated in industrial compatible and scalable solar cell fabrication have been demonstrated.

In this work, we utilize R2R UV NIL for improving the light absorption in industrial-compatible and fully scalable OSCs. The nanostructured diffraction grating is produced onto flexible Polyethyleneterephthalat (PET) by a R2R HoloPrint® process⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹. All the layers in the OSCs except the silver electrode are made using Sheet-to-Sheet (S2S) slot-die coating, whereas silver electrodes are deposited using R2R vacuum sputter deposition^{19,21}, to form ITO-free, flexible and scalable OSCs. All the processes are made in an ambient condition from non-toxic solvents and can be easily adapted to the industrial standard. Using optical modelling the effect of the nanostructure grating on the performance of OSCs is investigated, which validates the improvements observed in light absorption arising from the nanostructures. We present NG assisted flexible OSCs based on the non-fullerene acceptor system PBDB-T:ITIC, made from all industrial compatible methods, yielding a 15% improvement in PCE due to the embedded nanostructures.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The non-fullerene acceptor (ITIC) has been intensively studied in combination with novel donor PBDB-T due to their high performance and enhanced charge separation efficiency^{14,17,18,60-62}. In recent years, PBDB-T:ITIC based OSCs device reported efficiency of around 11% for spin-coated, small area laboratory device⁶³, and around 10% efficiency for large area scalable device on ITO/glass substrate^{64,65}. Even air-processing using flexible substrates with ITO and ITO-free configurations have been reported reaching efficiencies of 7.4%⁶⁶ and 5.5%²⁹, respectively. Figure 1 a) demonstrates the layout of the nanostructured assisted OSCs developed from the slot-die coating in this work. For planar reference devices, OSCs without any NG were also fabricated. The bottom electrode (Ag) overlaid with top PEDOT:PSS defines the active area of the solar cell which is 5.2 cm². Recently, PCE levels up to 5.5% was demonstrated for this material system and device configuration, using all-scalable air-processing on flexible ITO-free substrates²⁹. Here we furthermore embed the use of Xylene as a green processing solvent for these devices.

Figure 1 : a) Device stack for the nanostructured assisted PBDB-T:ITIC organic photovoltaics (OPV) cells. b) Small scale PBDB-T:ITIC OSC devices made by S2S slot-die coating. c) Chemical structure of the electron donor PBDB-T and the non-fullerene electron acceptor ITIC. d) Absorbance spectrum of a 200 nm PBDB-T:ITIC active layer deposited from the slot-die coating process.

Characterizations of NG assisted OSCs

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images of the PET/nanostructures, PET/ nanostructures/Ag, PET/ nanostructures/Ag/Al doped ZnO, and PET/ nanostructures/Ag/Al doped ZnO/PBDB-T:ITIC are shown in Figure 2. Both the surface morphology and step height between patterns can be observed in these images. A 210 nm step height between the grating top to bottom on the PET substrate is observed in **Error! Reference source not found. a)**, showing also the 1D symmetrical grating pattern

along the surface. From Figure 2 b) it can be also observed that the Ag electrode coating, deposited in a R2R DC magnetron sputter system, is conformal, and the step height is almost the same as for PET/nanostructured surface. This is essential to promote light scattering and enhancement of the optical light path in the cells. Figure 2 c) and d), show the surface topography for the slot die coating of ZnO and PBDB-T:ITIC layers on top of the Ag coated nanostructures, demonstrating only partially conformal coating with the step height reduced to 120 nm for ZnO, and between 10-60 nm for the active layer, depending on film thickness. Figure 2 e) shows the cross-sectional profile AFM images.

Figure 2 : AFM images of a) nanostructure surface on PET foil, b) Ag deposited on the nanostructured foils. c) Al doped ZnO deposited on the nanostructured Ag coated foils. and d) PBDB-T:ITIC deposited on the Al-doped ZnO/Ag/nanostructured foils. e) Cross-sectional profile of AFM images.

Photovoltaic properties of fabricated inverted OSCs

Figure 3, shows the J–V characteristics of PBDB-T:ITIC device (reference and nanostructured devices) as a function of active layer thickness, where the corresponding performance parameters are listed in Table 1 and Table 2. For low active layer thicknesses of 170 nm, the device performance of reference and nanostructured cells are quite similar, also on all IV parameters. With increasing active layer thicknesses, the performance of the reference cells increases slightly up to 200 nm thicknesses, mainly due to a slight increase in FF that appears to arise from an increased shunt resistance. Hereafter the performance of the reference cells drops slightly when further increasing the active layer thicknesses up to 260 nm. This drop appears to be J_{sc} driven. We note that the V_{oc} remains rather constant in these devices upon modifying the thickness. For the nanostructured cells, the performance increases monotonically with active layer thickness, arising from an increase in both FF and J_{sc} . A drop in the series resistance and small improvement in shunt resistance is seen for the thick active layer nanostructured cells, which can explain the improvements in FF. We note that similar FF improvements have been demonstrated by modelling the electrical properties of such nanostructured OSCs³¹. This FF improvement is mainly arising from an increased interfacial area between the active layer and the back contact which in turn improves the charge carrier extraction, as well as reducing losses during the free charge carrier transport towards the electron transport layer. As the nanostructured dimensions and active layer thicknesses utilized here are comparable to that study³¹, we believe this could explain the FF improvements. The J_{sc} improvements can be explained by the increase in active layer absorption by the light-trapping nanostructures, which will be analysed in more detail in the following.

Figure 3: PCE, J_{sc} , the open-circuit voltage V_{oc} , and FF of the OSCs with different thickness of PBDB-T:ITIC deposited on PET foil and NG. (Each set corresponds to 1 sigma of at least eight solar cells).

Thickness (nm)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE (%)	FF
170	11.14±0.53	0.83±0.01	4.21±0.17	0.45±0.01
190	10.89±0.73	0.81±0.01	4.06±0.62	0.46±0.04
200	11.84±0.55	0.81±0.01	4.69±0.34	0.49±0.01
220	10.81±0.37	0.82±0.01	4.25±0.28	0.48±0.02
260	10.78±0.11	0.82±0.01	4.27±0.30	0.48±0.04

Table 1: Statistics of PCE, J_{sc} , V_{oc} , and FF of the reference OSC devices for different thickness of PBDB-T:ITIC deposited on PET foil. Average values (1 sigma) extracted from at least eight solar cell devices.

Thickness (nm)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE (%)	FF
170	11.43±0.90	0.84±0.01	4.27±0.31	0.45±0.03
190	11.85±0.57	0.84±0.01	4.64±0.35	0.47±0.02
200	13.51±0.83	0.82±0.01	4.84±0.29	0.44±0.02
220	13.03±0.14	0.84±0.01	5.22±0.11	0.48±0.01
260	12.65±0.63	0.84±0.01	5.42±0.44	0.51±0.02

Table 2: Statistics of PCE, J_{sc} , V_{oc} , and FF of the nanostructured OSC for different thickness of PBDB-T:ITIC deposited on the NG. Average values (1 sigma) extracted from at least eight solar cell devices.

Figure 4a shows the J–V characteristics of champion devices of PBDB-T:ITIC based OSCs deposited on PET foil and NG. The corresponding performance parameters are shown in Table 3. We note that the J_{sc} was enhanced by 15% for the nanostructured device compared to the reference device, along with an enhancement in FF by 7%, as explained above. A very small improvement in V_{oc} for the nanostructured device is also seen. Overall, this is resulting in a 25% enhancement in PCE for the nanostructured devices. As expected, the EQE of the nanostructured device was improved compared to the reference device in the entire visible region as shown in Figure 4b, due to the presence of NG that diffracts the light towards the absorber layer, being present at the Ag back reflector, to enhance the optical path length and thus absorption.

Figure 4 : a) JV curves of the champion devices of PBDB-T: ITIC based OSCs deposited on PET foil and NG. b) EQE of Nanostructured and Reference based PBDB-T: ITIC OSCs

	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE (%)	FF
PET Foil	12.36	0.83	5.22	0.51
Nanostructured Grating	14.18	0.85	6.54	0.54

Table 3: Values of the J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF of champion devices of PBDB-T:ITIC based OSCs deposited on PET foil and NG.

Reflectance spectra from the entire reference and nanostructured device is shown in Figure 5a, with the reflectance ratio, defined as the reflectance from the nanostructured device over the reference device, shown in Figure 5b. These were obtained by using a UV-VIS spectrometer in an optical microscope setup, measured through an objective in reflectance mode. Having zero transmittance through the thick Ag back reflector, this becomes a measure of absorption. Figure 5a shows that the reflectance of the nanostructured devices is attenuated in comparison to the reference device, indicating an increase in absorption of the incident light in the presence of the nanostructures. This is further highlighted in Figure 5b, directly showing the reflectance ratio between the nanostructured

and reference device. We note that since this is measured through an objective, it includes incoming light at various angles. While this is relevant for solar cells in real applications, it cannot be used to compare directly to the enhancement in EQE, as this is measured only at normal incidence. However, it does verify the improved absorption in the nanostructured solar cell devices. To shed further light on this, we conducted optical modelling of the nanostructured solar cells and compared that to the reference solar cells.

Figure 5: a) Reflectance ratio between nanostructured/reference device and the bare silver deposited on PET foil. b) Reflectance ratio between nanostructured device and reference device

Figure 6a illustrates the reference film and nanostructured film stacks employed in the calculations. The selected geometries resemble the experimental ones. The Ag layer is composed of 100 nm thick substrate and a 200 nm high grating. The Al-doped ZnO layer is composed of 30 nm substrate and a grating with a fixed height of 120 nm. The period of the Ag grating, and correspondingly the period of the Al-doped ZnO grating, is set to 500 nm. The thickness of the PBDB-T:ITIC layer varies between 170 nm and 270 nm, and the thickness of the PEDOT:PSS layer is set to 175 nm. In the following, we approximate the presence of the subwavelength grating such as affecting only the Ag and the Al-doped ZnO layers. For the sake of simplicity, we fix the width of the Ag

grating lines to 400 nm and vary the width of the Al-doped ZnO (W) lines. Obviously, in practice W depends on the width of the Ag lines, but this effect is not considered in the following examination.

Figure 6b shows the absorptivity spectra for the reference film and for the nanostructured film with various values of W . Evidently, for any W value the absorptivity of the nanostructured film is higher, which reflects the expected light trapping enhancement involved with the incorporation of subwavelength gratings. Interestingly, the main modulation of both the reference and the nanostructure spectra is due to Fabry-Perot oscillations which is also apparent in the EQE spectra presented in Figure 4b. The incorporation of the grating results in slight shifts in peak position relative to the reference sample. Importantly, both the absorptivity spectra of Figure 6b and the EQE spectrum of Figure 4b show significant broadband absorption in the spectral range of 400-700 nm. Such broadband absorption enhancement is characteristic of densely packed nanopillar arrays (for example), whereas diluted nanopillar arrays present specific absorptivity peaks related to the excitation of radial leaky modes⁶⁷.

Figure 6c shows the dependency of the absorptivity spectra on both W and PBDB-T:ITIC thickness. The absorptivity spectra of the reference film are presented as well. It is evident that smaller W entails higher absorptivity values. Figure 6d presents the respective broadband absorption as well as the broadband absorption dependency on the PBDB-T:ITIC thickness. Note that both the reference and the nanostructured film show highest broadband absorption for PBDB-T:ITIC thickness of 270 nm, with about 7% enhancement for the nanostructured film of $W=100$ nm compared with the reference film. Finally, Figure 6e presents the distributions of the absorbed photon density (APD) for the various W values, as well as for the reference sample, under broadband illumination with 1.5AM global solar spectrum (the direction of the impinging electric field is shown as well). Clearly, the incorporation of subwavelength grating generates complex 3D optical excitations that are not present in the reference film, which is governed by multiple Fresnel reflections associated

with planar surfaces. While some deviation from experimental condition will occur such as surface roughness, coating uniformity etc, and thus we cannot expect to match quantitatively the experimental values, we note that clear optical absorption enhancements are seen for similar grating dimensions as those used experimentally, and thus the optical modelling can clearly account of the absorption and J_{sc} enhancements observed experimentally.

Figure 6 : Finite-difference time-domain electromagnetic calculations of nanostructured films. a) Illustrations of the calculated stacks. b) The dependency of the absorptivity spectra on W . c) The dependency of the absorptivity spectra on W and PBDB-T:ITIC thickness. d) The dependency of the broadband absorption under the illumination of AM1.5G. e) APD distributions under the illumination of AM1.5G.

CONCLUSION

A novel method for integration of fully scalable R2P processed nanostructures into scalable and industrial compatible flexible OSCs is demonstrated. The NG are introduced on PET foils and integrated at the back reflector side of the OSCs to enhance the optical path length in the cells, and thus the optical absorption. In addition, the nanostructured current collectors, i.e. electrodes and transport layers, also lead to improved charge carrier extraction in the devices. Devices are realized by slot-die coating of the non-fullerene acceptor based PBDB-T:ITIC system in air, using green solvents and flexible, ITO-free device configuration. The PCE is increased by 25% in the presence of a nanostructured topology, which is governed mainly by a 15% enhancement in J_{sc} and 7% enhancement in FF. The large J_{sc} enhancement is supported by optical modelling confirming the absorption enhancement. The best devices reach a PCE of 6.5%, which is the highest reported for air-processed slot-die coated ITO-free PBDB-T:ITIC devices, here using non-toxic solvents i.e. fully industrial compatible. Our work demonstrates the possibility of scaling of flexible non-fullerene acceptor based OSCs with light-trapping nanostructured foils following industrial standards, and thus potentially to produce large areas of such solar cells at low cost and high throughput.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Figure 1 a) shows the OSCs structure used in this study. Heat stabilized PET foils with a thickness of 125 μm (Melinex ST505) were purchased from DuPont Teijin Films. Aluminium doped ZnO (H-Genes'Ink H-DZ41006) was purchased from Genes'ink and was in-line filtered with a 0.25 μm PS membrane from Whatman. PBDB-T and ITIC were purchased from Brilliant Matters Inc. All chemicals were used as received without any further purification. The active layer solution was prepared with a ratio of 1:1 (PBDB-T:ITIC) at a total concentration of 24 mg ml^{-1} in Xylene. The solution was stirred at 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3h in ambient conditions. FHC solar were purchased from Heraeus. FHC solar is diluted in Hypergrade I-Propanol in the ratio 1:1, to get the required thickness.

OSCs Fabrication

OSCs were fabricated with an inverted device structure of PET/Ag/Al-doped ZnO/PBDB-T:ITIC/FHC PEDOT:PSS for the reference devices and PET/ nanostructured diffraction grating/Ag/Al-doped ZnO/PBDB-T:ITIC/FHC PEDOT:PSS for the photonic enhanced devices. The nanostructured diffraction grating is produced onto flexible PET by an R2P NIL process by Stensborg A/S. In this process, the foil was partially coated with an imprinting resin X166b using a wire bar coater. The coated substrate was processed using a HoloPrint® uniA6 DT Roll-To-Plate UV nanoimprint lithography machine, where a flexible imprinting template was used to replicate the structures as shown in Experimental Figure 7. Various imprinting conditions were tested between up to 6 m/min. The curing of the imprinting resin was done under a 395nm UV-LED lamp. All imprinted samples undergo a post-cure procedure using an iron-doped gas discharge UV source via UVACube 100 by Hönle UV technology. All devices were processed in ambient condition, except for the silver electrode which was deposited under vacuum condition. For Silver deposition, PET and nanostructured grating substrate were pre-treated with DC argon plasma in vacuum for 120 s, and silver of 100 nm was through a shadow mask that defines the active area of the solar cells. The entire

process of sputtering the electrodes was done in an R2R vacuum line. Al-doped ZnO, PBDB-T:ITIC, FHC PEDOT:PSS were deposited consecutively by slot die coating. The coating setup is shown in the supporting Figure S2. It consists of a motorized film applicator (Erichsen COATMASTER 510), which was custom modified for slot-die coating and a vacuum plate for substrate fixture, and a heating element for substrate heating. The syringe pump (Harvard Apparatus PHD 2000) was used to control ink delivery. The syringe was placed in a custom build aluminium sleeve which was heated with silicon heated pads. A custom build slot die head was fabricated from stainless steel, and it can be heated with the support of a heating cartridge. Shims and meniscus guides were used to limit the coating of Al-doped ZnO and PBDB-T:ITIC to 11 mm. To avoid shunting and define the active area of cells, the width is limited to 7 mm for FHC PEDOT:PSS.

After the electrode is deposited on the substrate by DC magnetron sputtering, Al-doped zinc was slot die coated with a coating speed of 12 mm s^{-1} at a pumping speed of 0.05 ml min^{-1} and vacuum plate at ambient temperature. The gap between the slot-die meniscus guide and the substrate surface was $500 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. After the coating, the film was annealed in a vacuum oven at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min. The vacuum plate was heated up to $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the rest of the process. Slot-die coating of the active layer was performed with a coating speed of 6.3 mm s^{-1} , and the pumping speed were varied between 0.035 to $0.055 \text{ ml min}^{-1}$. During the coating process, both the slot-die head and the syringe were heated to $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the vacuum plate was heated up to $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The coating gap distance was kept at $200 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ during the coating process. This resulted in an active layer thickness between 170 to 260 nm. The PEDOT:PSS FHC Solar solution was coated directly following the coating of the active layer, using a coating speed of 12 mm s^{-1} and a pumping speed of 0.13 ml min^{-1} . In the end, the entire stack was glued on a glass substrate ($15 \times 15 \text{ mm}$) using 105 instant adhesives from Permabond, followed by encapsulation with the barrier material. Delo KATIOBOND LP655 was used as encapsulation glue, which was cured under UV light (365 nm and 400 nm wavelength) for 15 min.

Experimental Figure 7: HoloPrint® - Stensborg nano imprinting technology.

Film and device characterization

OPV cells were characterized under a 3000 class AAA solar simulator from Abet Technologies Inc. providing AM1.5G light of 100 mWcm^{-2} . The light intensity was calibrated at 100 mWcm^{-2} by using an Oriel reference cell. J–V curves were recorded with a source meter Keithley 2400 under ambient atmosphere. The surface morphology of the thin films was measured using AFM operating in tapping mode under ambient conditions and the thickness using DEKTAK profilometer. EQE measurement of devices were measured from the PVE300 photovoltaic QE system from Bentham. The reflectance spectrum of the entire device was measured using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer, which is used in a setup that integrates the spectrometer in a light microscope employing a white light illumination.

Three dimensional finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) electromagnetic calculations

The ElectroMagnetic Wave (EMW) solver by Synopsys Inc. is employed for the 3D calculations. The calculations are executed for a single unit cell of an infinite square lattice using periodic boundary conditions along the lateral x-y directions. Complementary perfectly matched layer boundary conditions are employed along the vertical direction. Plane wave excitation is used in the spectral range of 400-1100 nm. At each wavelength the total number of reflected, transmitted, and absorbed

photons is considered using sensors surrounding the unit cell. In this way the absorptivity, reflectivity and transmissivity are achieved. Also, at each wavelength the absorbed photon density (APD) is calculated. The broadband absorption of the solar radiation is calculated by weighting the absorptivity with the standard AM1.5G solar spectrum. The optical values of the materials are taken from reference^{68–71}.

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